

1 N33S, 7 S33N

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 N33S, 7 S33N

S
N

- Bathybatini
- Benthochromini
- Boulengerochromini
- Cyphotilapiini
- Cyprichromini
- Ectodini
- Eretmodini
- Gobiocichlini
- Haplochromini
- Heterotilapini
- Lamprologini
- Limnochromini
- Perissodini
- Serranochromini
- Steatocranini
- Tilapiini
- Trematocarini
- Tropheini

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 N33S, 7 S33N

S
N

shallow
intermediate
deep
NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 N33S, 7 S33N

● S
● N

■ shallow
■ intermediate
■ deep
■ NA

0 2 4 6 8 10 12